

STUDYING THE PHARMACOLOGICAL EFFECTIVENESS OF THE USE OF THE DRUG "ADVANTAN" ON THE COURSE OF ATOPIC DERMATITIS IN CHILDREN

Mamarizaev Ibrohim Komilzhonovich

Assistant, Department of Pediatrics No. 1 and Neonatology, Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10702430>

Abstract: And topical dermatitis has a chronic relapsing course, is often complicated by secondary infection and requires adequate and constant external therapy. This article is devoted to a review of the clinical effects of the external use of Advantan for atopic dermatitis (AD).

Keywords: children, allergies, Advantan, dermatitis, antihistamines

ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ФАРМАКОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ПРЕПАРАТА «АДВАНТАН» ПРИ ТЕЧЕНИИ АТОПИЧЕСКОГО ДЕРМАТИТА У ДЕТЕЙ

Аннотация: А местный дерматит имеет хроническое рецидивирующее течение, часто осложняется вторичной инфекцией и требует адекватной и постоянной наружной терапии. Статья посвящена обзору клинических эффектов наружного применения Адвантана при атопическом дерматите (АД).

Ключевые слова: дети, аллергия, Адвантан, дерматит, антигистаминные препараты.

RELEVANCE

Allergic diseases are one of the common causes of impaired social activity, early disability of children and the young working population, which brings enormous economic damage and determines its medical and social significance.

Official statistics data are based, as a rule, on indicators obtained when patients visited a medical institution. Over the past 10 years, information has accumulated on the high level of allergic diseases in the regions of the Russian Federation. Inconsistency between official statistics and epidemiological studies, as well as the influence of epidemiological conditions in the region on the morbidity level of the population (6).

Official statistics data are based, as a rule, on indicators obtained when patients visited a medical institution. Over the past 10 years, information has accumulated on the high level of allergic diseases in the regions of the Russian Federation. Inconsistency between official statistics and epidemiological studies, as well as the influence of epidemiological conditions in the region on the morbidity level of the population (5).

It is obvious that the growth of allergic diseases in the world is associated with changes in the socio-economic level of development of society. A sharp deterioration of the environment, including man-made disasters, acute and chronic stress, without control, widespread use of medications, especially those with dufane properties, those that can be deposited in the body. Widespread use of synthetic products. Durable introduction into everyday life of means for disinfection and disinfestation, changes in dietary patterns, and the emergence of new allergens.

Studies conducted by authors from Russia and neighboring countries have shown (2,4,6) that intensive incidence rates of allergic diseases fluctuate sharply from 11.4 to 233.8 per 1000 adult population, it is believed that this is due to the rapid development of the chemical industry,

environmental pollution, products of incomplete combustion of fuel, waste emissions from industrial enterprises, and an increase in the demand for various medicines.

It is obvious that the growth of allergic diseases in the world is associated with changes in the socio-economic level of development of society. A sharp deterioration of the environment, including man-made disasters, acute and chronic stress, without control, widespread use of medications, especially those with dufane properties, those that can be deposited in the body. Widespread use of synthetic products. Durable introduction into everyday life of means for disinfection and disinfestation, changes in dietary patterns, and the emergence of new allergens.

Studies conducted by authors from Russia and neighboring countries have shown (1,3,5) that intensive incidence rates of allergic diseases fluctuate sharply from 11.4 to 233.8 per 1000 adult population; it is believed that this is due to the rapid development of the chemical industry, environmental pollution, products of incomplete combustion of fuel, waste emissions from industrial enterprises, and an increase in the demand for various medicines. Studies conducted by authors from Russia and neighboring countries have shown that intensive incidence rates of allergic diseases fluctuate sharply from 11.4 to 233.8 per 1000 adult population, they believe that this is due to the rapid development of the chemical industry, environmental pollution, products of incomplete combustion fuel, waste emissions from industrial enterprises, and an increase in the demand for various medicines.

Allergic diseases registered in adolescents, including bronchial asthma, in most cases have their onset in early, preschool and school age; the manifestation of clinical manifestations of allergies and asthma is comparatively less common in adolescence. In cases of clinical manifestations of atopy at an early age in the form of atopic dermatitis, allergic rhinitis and bronchial asthma, gastrointestinal allergies, the cause of their occurrence is usually sensitization to food allergens.

The latter factors include cow's milk proteins, eggs, cereals, and fish. Medicines also cause allergies and sulfonamides have a slight sensitizing effect. The most common allergic diseases among the population include bronchial asthma among the entire population of the Lipetsk region, which ranks second - 34.3%, among adults - 38.4%, among adolescents - 31.01%, and children 20.6%. Contact dermatitis occupies a special place among allergic diseases. In the structure of allergic diseases, contact dermatitis ranks first among the entire population and accounts for 44.9%, among the adult population - 44.52%, among adolescents - 40.57%, and among children - 45.19%. Allergic rhinitis in Russia affects from 12 to 24% of the population.

Currently, the problem of allergies is extremely relevant all over the world, notes E.V. Glushko in his dissertation. (24). The dissertation author points out that up to 40% of the general population and 10-12% of the child population suffer from various allergic diseases. The prevalence of asthma ranges from 5 to 10% in Russia; these figures reach up to 14%.

Purpose of the study: to study the effectiveness of Advantan and eubiotic On the course of atopic dermatitis in children.

MATERIALS AND RESEARCH METHODS

To study the effectiveness of Advantan and the eubiotic , 66 children were examined. The first group of patients received a traditional method of therapy: diet therapy, hypoallergenic medicinal creams, antihistamines. The second group of patients received complex therapy together with Advantan - 0.1% ointment + eubiotic . The drug " Advantan " was used once a day for 2 weeks, given its prolonged action. The effectiveness of the drug was assessed by the condition of

such clinical manifestations as itching, hyperemia, and polymorphic skin rashes. The effectiveness of the eubiotic was assessed by improving the state of the microbiota in children.

RESULTS RESEARCH THEIR DISCUSSIONS

Evaluation of the effectiveness of AD therapy with Advantan in the form of an ointment for external use for 14 days was significantly more effective. Thus, there was a faster dynamics of relief of clinical manifestations of atopic dermatitis in patients of the main group compared to the control group. Consequently, itching of the skin was noted in 33 (80%), dry skin in 28 (68%), erythema in 23 (56%), feelings of skin tightness in 17 (41%) and sleep disturbance in 27 (66%) children of the main group. And in children of the control group, skin itching was noted in 32 (86%), dry skin in 26 (70%), erythema in 21 (56%), skin tightness in 15 (40%) and sleep disturbance in 25 (67%). As can be seen from the results of examination and treatment of atopic dermatitis in children, the use of 10% zinc sulfate ointment as a basic therapy for 10-14 days was accompanied by rapid positive dynamics. The results were assessed on the SCORAD itching scale - group I 1.1 and group II 1.4; dry skin – group I 0.8 and group II 1.4; erythema – group I 1.4 and group II 2.04; feelings of skin tightening – group I 1.3; Group II 1.7; sleep disorders – group I 1.0 and group II 1.5 points. By 10-14 days, skin itching disappeared in 32 (78%) children in group I and 27 (72%) in group II; dry skin in 27 (67%) children of the main group and 24 (64%) of the control group; erythema 23 (56%) – group I and 19 (51%) – group II; feelings of skin tightness 16 (39%) - group I and 13 (37%) - in children of group II, sleep disturbances 25 (61%) - group I and 22 (59%) in children of group II.

Improvement in general condition was observed at 3.25 ± 0.23 days from the start of treatment, whereas in the first group of patients who did not receive Advantan and the eubiotic at 5.3 ± 0.18 . We detected a pronounced therapeutic effect in the second group of patients on 6.62 ± 0.19 days, and in the first group on 8.74 ± 0.21 days from the onset of the course.

CONCLUSIONS

The drug " Advantan " was used once a day for 2 weeks, given its prolonged action, the effectiveness of the drug was assessed according to the status of such clinical manifestations as itching, hyperemia, and polymorphic skin rashes. The effectiveness of the eubiotic was assessed by improving the state of the microbiota in children. The work carried out also showed the effectiveness of the drug " Advantan " and eubiotics on clinical and laboratory-instrumental indicators of atopic dermatitis in children.

Bibliography:

1. Wollenberg A. et al. Atopic Dermatitis in Children and Adults: Diagnosis and Treatment //Deutsches Ärzteblatt International. – 2023. – T. 120. – №. 13. – C. 224.
2. Wollenberg A. et al. Atopic Dermatitis in Children and Adults: Diagnosis and Treatment //Deutsches Ärzteblatt International. – 2023. – T. 120. – №. 13. – C. 224.
3. Fedorovna I. M. The influence of risk factors on developing atypical pneumonia in young children //Asian journal of pharmaceutical and biological research. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 2.
4. Fedorovna I. M. The influence of risk factors on developing atypical pneumonia in young children //Asian journal of pharmaceutical and biological research. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 2.
5. Askarovna S. O. et al. Correlation of hormonal status indicators of physical and sexual development in children with chronic bronchitis //European Science Review. – 2017.
6. Fedorovna I. M. et al. IMPROVED DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF ATYPICAL PNEUMONIA IN CHILDREN //Thematics Journal of Applied Sciences. – 2023. – T. 7. – №. 1.